

1 **Effects of indigenous soil cyanobacteria on seed germination and seedling**
2 **growth of arid species used in restoration**

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 *Background and aims*

18 Cyanobacteria from biocrusts can enhance soil function and structure, a critical objective when restoring
19 degraded dryland ecosystems. Large-scale restoration of biodiversity requires direct seeding of native plant
20 species, and bio-priming seeds with cyanobacteria is potentially of high benefit. The utility of cyanobacteria
21 for improving soil is therefore dependent on whether target plant species remain unaffected during its
22 application.

23 *Methods*

24 Cyanobacteria from the genera *Microcoleus* and *Nostoc* were isolated from locally-sourced biocrust
25 samples, and cultured under controlled conditions. A two-factor laboratory experiment was conducted
26 including cyanobacteria and the culture growth medium (BG11) as factors. We bio-primed seeds of five
27 species native to Western Australia, commonly used in dryland restoration, by soaking them in the cultures
28 developed, and assessed germination and growth.

29 *Results*

30 We found significant positive effects of seeds bio-primed with cyanobacteria on germination and seedling
31 growth of two species, *Senna notabilis* and *Acacia hilliana*, respectively. Importantly, no significant
32 negative effects of cyanobacteria were found for any of the species studied.

33 *Conclusions*

34 Few studies of cyanobacteria effects on regeneration of native species exist. We found that the potential
35 benefits of applying indigenous bacteria via bio-priming seeds would not inhibit plant establishment, and
36 indeed may be beneficial for some species used in dryland restoration.

37 **Keywords**

38 Pilbara, drylands, biocrust, native plants, seedling recruitment, Drylands; land rehabilitation, bio-priming.

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Millions of hectares of drylands are being degraded each year, and restoring these areas is a global priority
41 within the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations 2030 Agenda ([Keesstra et al. 2018](#)). A
42 critical challenge for successful restoration in dryland ecosystems is ensuring that suitable soil substrates
43 with viable seedbanks are available to support plant establishment ([Muñoz-Rojas et al. 2016a](#)). Given the
44 large scale of disturbance from human activities such as mining, and the subsequent scale of restoration
45 required, direct seeding is often the only viable means for restoring diverse and functional native vegetation
46 communities ([Erickson et al. 2017](#)). This seeding effort can only be justifiable if seeds surpass the crucial
47 life-history stages of seed germination and seedling emergence ([Merino-Martin et al. 2016](#)). These early
48 phases of plant establishment involve many interlinked transitions ([Erickson et al. 2017](#); [Larson and Funk](#)
49 [2016](#)) and seed regeneration is the foundation for the recovery of functional native plant communities and
50 thus, the persistence and maintenance of terrestrial biodiverse ecosystems worldwide ([Jiménez-Alfaro et](#)
51 [al. 2016](#); [Miller et al. 2017](#); [Perring et al. 2015](#)).

52 Biological crusts, or biocrusts, are communities of microscopic and macroscopic organisms that live in the
53 upper surface of soils ([Büdel et al. 2016](#); [Chilton et al. 2017](#)). Cyanobacteria are major components of
54 biocrust and consist of, oxygenic, photosynthetic bacteria capable of surviving in extreme environmental
55 conditions and tolerate high temperatures, desiccation, extreme pH and salinity ([Singh et al. 2016](#); [Williams](#)
56 [et al. 2014](#)). In recent years, studies have highlighted the key role of cyanobacteria as ‘ecological engineers’
57 in drylands by enhancing soil function and structure ([Antoninka et al. 2016](#); [Bowker 2007](#); [Park et al. 2017](#)).
58 These organisms are one of the most promising microorganisms used as bio-fertilizer as they produce active
59 compounds that enhance plant growth and improve overall soil conditions ([Singh et al. 2016](#)). Some
60 cyanobacteria species are able to release exopolysaccharides (EPS) that work as a cement, increasing soil
61 stability, crusting, and moisture-holding capacity ([Rossi et al. 2017](#)). But these substances have also shown
62 a potential for increasing germination of desert plants ([Song et al. 2017](#)). Thus, the cyanobacteria culture
63 medium, where EPS are excreted, has been proposed as a nutrient supplement to promote succession of

64 artificial cyanobacterial biocrust ([Xu et al. 2013](#)), and could also be used as an inoculant to promote other
65 early plant recruitment processes. However, the effects of cyanobacteria on the early plant life-history
66 stages of germination and seedling growth are uncertain and warrant investigation. Most of the available
67 studies addressing the use of cyanobacteria as bio-fertilizer have been conducted in plants used in
68 agriculture, such as rice or wheat crops ([Singh et al. 2016](#)). The few studies conducted in natural ecosystems
69 have shown contrasting results that include positive, negative, or uncorrelated interactions between vascular
70 plants and cyanobacteria species ([Song et al. 2017](#); [Su et al. 2009](#); [Zhang et al. 2016](#); [Zaady et al. 1997](#)).
71 Thus, the utility of cyanobacteria as a way of enhancing soil function and structure is dependent on whether
72 the associated plant species targeted for restoration remain unaffected during its application, or even benefit
73 from it. To our knowledge, no studies investigating the effects of cyanobacteria on bio-primed seeds in a
74 restoration context currently exist.

75 Here, we assessed the early-stage transitions of germination and seedling growth of seeds bio-primed with
76 locally-sourced indigenous cyanobacteria for five native species used in arid land restoration (*Acacia*
77 *hilliana*, *Senna notabilis*, *Grevillea wickhamii*, *Triodia epactia* and *Triodia wiseana*). These species cover
78 a range of genera (Table 1), are native to the Pilbara region (an arid, biodiverse region of north-west Western
79 Australia) and are targeted for use in restoration after intensive mining activities have ceased ([Bateman et](#)
80 [al., 2016](#); [Erickson et al. 2017](#); [Muñoz-Rojas et al. 2016b](#)).

81 **2. Materials and methods**

82 *2.1 Cyanobacteria culturing and selection*

83 A polyphasic approach combining whole community 16S rDNA profiling as well as culturing was used to
84 identify candidate cyanobacterial strains that were both representative of the native community and able to
85 be up-scaled for scalable growth trials (Table 2). Soil biocrust samples were collected from two
86 cyanobacteria-dominated biological soil crusts free of mosses, lichens and plant material near Gallery Hill
87 in the Pilbara Region of Western Australia (21°37.416'S, 119°02.303'E) in May 2009. Samples were taken

88 from the upper 10 mm and transported in air-tight zip lock bags to the University of New South Wales
89 (UNSW, Sydney, Australia) and stored at 4°C until processing in July 2009 (Fig. 1).

90 Bacterial profiling was performed upon whole-community DNA extracted using the FastDNA SPIN Kit
91 for Soil (MP Biomedicals) as per the manufacturer's instructions. Genomic DNA was submitted to RTL
92 Genomics (Lubbock, Texas) where pyrosequencing of the 16S rDNA was conducted using the universal
93 bacterial primers 28F/519R. Pyrosequencing data from each site was combined and analysed using standard
94 approaches ([Schloss et al 2011](#)) resulting in 16093 high-quality reads across 2840 OTUs formed at 97%
95 similarity (see Supplementary Material for further detail, Fig. S1). The majority of sequences (78%) were
96 cyanobacterial according to GreenGenes (McDonald et al 2012) taxonomic assignment and comprised of a
97 diverse range of genera dominated by the families Oscillatoriophycideae and Nostocophycideae (42.4%
98 and 41.8% of sequences, respectively) (Fig. 2). These families typify two distinct morphotypes: large,
99 simple filamentous able to form tightly interwoven mats (Oscillatoriophycideae) and long, heterocystic
100 types which produce scytonemin-containing gelatinous sheaths (Nostocophycideae).

101 Cyanobacteria cultures were isolated as in Rippka et al. ([1988](#)) and identified to species via microscopy,
102 BLAST analysis and phylogeny (see Supplementary Material for further detail, Table S1). The species
103 identified (Table 2) were distinct from those detected via community profiling using the Greengenes
104 database, however, this was not unexpected due to the problematic nature of cyanobacterial classification
105 ([Garcia-Pichel et al. 1996](#)). For example, *Microcoleus* and *Phormidium* are phenotypically and ecologically
106 similar and are poorly resolved phylogenetically ([Garcia-Pichel et al. 2013](#)). We sought to select candidate
107 cyanobacteria species which were both representative of the dominant morphotypes detected via
108 pyrosequencing and that exhibited sufficient growth of biomass for bio-priming. Based on this criteria and
109 our findings we selected isolates corresponding to *Microcoleus paludosus* (Oscillatoriophycideae) and
110 *Nostoc microscopicum* (Nostocophycideae) (Fig.1). These taxa have a broad presence in Australian and
111 arid lands worldwide ([Büdel et al. 2016](#); [Chilton et al. 2017](#); [Williams et al. 2014](#)). Optimal cyanobacterial
112 growth was achieved using deep-pan petri dishes using BG11 media at 25°C under constant 80 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$

113 ¹ of light. For bio-priming, culture mass for *Nostoc microscopicum* and *Microcoleus paludosus* was mixed
114 at a ratio of 50:50 to reflect the relative abundance of the two dominant morphotypes observed via
115 pyrosequencing. The mixed culture was filtered and oven dried to obtain the dry biomass, and re-suspended
116 in both distilled water (H₂O_d) and the culture growth BG11 to achieve a concentration of 1g/L in both
117 treatments.

118 2.2 Bio-priming of seeds with cyanobacteria

119 Seeds for each species were collected from wild plant populations in the Pilbara region of Western Australia
120 in Nov-Dec 2013. Seeds were stored in a controlled environment room at 15°C and 15% RH prior to
121 experimentation. Prior to germination testing, seeds of *A. hilliana* and *S. notabilis* were first treated to
122 overcome physical dormancy by placement for 1-2 min in hot water at 80-100 °C. Seeds of *Triodia* possess
123 physiological dormancy and these seeds were first removed from their covering floret structures that restrict
124 germination (following methods outlined in Erickson et al. (2016)). Non-viable seeds for all species were
125 removed via x-ray analysis to eliminate seed quality as a potential impediment to germination responses.
126 Seeds from all species were then surface sterilized in a 1% (w/v) calcium hypochlorite [Ca(OCl)₂] solution
127 for 30 min and rinsed before cyanobacteria bio-priming.

128 For each of the five plant species, a two-factor fully orthogonal experiment was conducted in the laboratory
129 in July 2017, with the application of cyanobacteria culture and the BG11 medium as the two factors. Seeds
130 were bio-primed with cyanobacteria in either an H₂O solution (CY+H₂O), or in the culture growth medium
131 BG11 solution (CY+BG11). H₂O_d as a control (Control-H₂O) and culture growth media without
132 cyanobacteria (Control-BG11) were also included. Seeds (n=100) were plated in replicated 90mm Petri
133 dishes (n=4 per treatment; 25 seeds per dish). Each dish was initially irrigated with 10mL of either H₂O or
134 BG11 solution, depending on treatment, and subsequently topped up with 2mL to prevent drying out.

135 Germination was scored as emergence of the radicle and checked daily for 7 d, and again at day 10.
136 Measurements of root and shoot lengths were undertaken on 7 day old seedlings. Ungerminated seeds were
137 assessed for viability after 17 d using a cut test (Ooi et al., 2004). Germination rate was calculated as the

138 time required to reach 50% of the total germination (T_{50}). Proportional data were analysed using
139 Generalised Linear Models (GLMs) with a binomial distribution (germination, seedling survival). A linear
140 model was used for analysing root/shoot lengths. The main factors tested for these data were BG11 medium
141 (yes or no) and cyanobacteria (yes or no). Post-hoc multiple comparisons were made using the package
142 *lsmeans*. All analyses were conducted using the R statistical platform Version 3.1.2 ([R Core Team 2017](#)).
143 The values of $P < 0.05$ were considered as statistically significant. Germination rate was calculated using
144 the R package *drc* (Ritz et al., 2005) with the time required to reach 50% of the total seeds germinated
145 (T_{50}). Comparisons between treatments were made using the *compParm* function.

146 **3. Results**

147 The polyphasic characterisation of cyanobacteria revealed a diverse array of genera exhibiting traits critical
148 for colonisation and survival within extreme arid conditions, including filamentous growth, heterocysts (for
149 Nostocophycideae), and EPS production (Table 2, Fig.2).

150 The best model for the germination of *Acacia hilliana* seeds included both factors, with a significant
151 interaction between cyanobacteria and BG11 ($df=1$, $\chi^2=7.4164$ $P=0.006$). Although *Acacia hilliana* seeds
152 germinated to similar proportions across all treatments, there was a small but significant positive effect of
153 the Control-BG11 treatment (Fig. 3a). However, a similar highly significant interaction found for *Acacia*
154 *hilliana* seedling survival ($df=1$, $\chi^2=14.652$ $P<0.001$) (Fig. 3b), and seedling shoot ($df=1,224$, $F=40.551$
155 $P<0.001$) and root growth ($df=1,224$, $F=32.852$ $P<0.001$) (Fig.4a, 4b), was driven by a strong negative
156 effect of the BG11 medium; seeds soaked in BG11 germinated but nearly all quickly died (mortality
157 measured at Day 17 for all seeds germinating by Day 6). The negative effect of the culture medium appeared
158 to be counteracted by the addition of cyanobacteria, as survival and seedling growth of *Acacia hilliana* was
159 not affected in seeds bio-primed with cyanobacteria + BG11 (Fig. 3, Fig. 4).

160 For *Senna notabilis*, the best fitting model for germination contained only the main effect of cyanobacteria
161 ($df=1$, $\chi^2=9.0091$ $P=0.003$). The addition of cyanobacteria had a significant positive effect on germination
162 in the presence of H_2O , and a positive but non-significant effect in the presence of BG11 solution (Fig. 3).

163 There were no effects on shoot growth, but a significant main effect of cyanobacteria on root growth
164 ($df=1,226$, $F=6.333$, $P=0.0125$). However, we did not find any significant differences between treatments
165 (with or without cyanobacteria added) within each level of media (Fig. 4b).

166 For all remaining species (*Grevillea* and the two *Triodia* species), there were no significant effects found
167 for germination, but several small effects on seedling survival or growth. There were significant main
168 negative effects of the BG11 medium on *Grevillea* ($df=1,88$, $F=2.107$, $P=0.004$) and *Triodia epactia* root
169 growth ($df=1,125$, $F=31.944$, $P<0.001$). For *Triodia wiseana*, there was a significant main effect of the
170 BG11 medium on shoot growth ($df=1,129$, $F=7.223$, $P=0.008$) and a significant interaction between the
171 two factors for root growth ($df=1,129$, $F=4.189$, $P=0.043$), driven mainly by a slight suppression of growth
172 with the BG11 medium (Fig. 3, Fig.4).

173 There were no clear differences found between treatments on the rate of germination (T_{50}) for any of the
174 study species. The only significant effect showed that cyanobacteria slowed germination rate slightly for
175 *Grevillea wickhamii* seeds in the BG11 solution (3.84 ± 0.15 versus 4.51 ± 0.22 days). *Senna notabilis* was
176 the fastest species, with a T_{50} of 0.08 days (cyanobacteria + water) ($0.08 - 0.32$ days across all treatments),
177 followed by *Triodia epactia* ($1.74 - 1.86$ days), *Triodia wiseana* ($1.67 - 2.08$ days), *Acacia hilliana* (2.62
178 $- 3.35$ days) and *Grevillea wickhamii* ($3.84 - 4.51$ days) (Fig. S2).

179 **4. Discussion**

180 *4.1 Effects of seed bio-priming with cyanobacteria on early developmental stages of native species*

181 Cyanobacteria and the BG11 medium had no effect on the germination and growth of *Grevillea wickhamii*
182 or the two *Triodia* species, meaning application of either as a nutrient supplement to promote artificial
183 cyanobacterial biocrusts would have little impact on the early life-history stages of these species, at least
184 within in the timeframe evaluated in this study. However, our results did show large significant effects on
185 aspects of *Acacia hilliana* and *Senna notabilis* germination, seedling survival and growth over the timeline
186 evaluated, suggesting that there may even be some beneficial effects of bio-priming seeds with indigenous
187 cyanobacteria. While there are some species specific differences in response, in agreement with previous

188 studies conducted in arid areas ([Song et al., 2017](#); [Zaady et al., 2007](#)), overall cyanobacteria did not have
189 an inhibitory effect on any of the species studied.

190 Seed germination and seedling growth are critical stages of plant development largely influenced by water
191 potential, air and soil temperature ([Arnold et al. 2014](#); [Ooi 2007](#); [Ooi et al. 2009](#)). Since biocrust
192 cyanobacteria can influence several soil characteristics such as soil structure, porosity, nutrient and water
193 availability ([Chamizo et al. 2012](#)), there are several ways in which cyanobacteria may influence germination
194 in the soil and therefore seed responses may be different in the field. . Subsequently, the formed biocrust
195 will have an effect on seedling emergence and plant establishment. Some studies have reported an inhibition
196 of seedling emergence, survival, and establishment with the appearance of biocrust as a response to the
197 species-specific interactions between vascular plants and forming biocrust ([Escudero et al. 2007](#); [Su et al.](#)
198 [2007](#)). Nevertheless, in most cases biocrusts had a positive effect on seedling growth caused by the increase
199 in soil N contents and the release of beneficial substances such as exopolysaccharides (EPS) ([Wang et al.](#)
200 [2009](#); [Xu et al. 2013](#)).

201 The biocrust community structure found here is comparable to early stage biocrusts in Australia ([Chilton](#)
202 [et al 2017](#)) and, globally, to Type 1 and 2 biocrusts from the Kalahari ([Elliott et al 2014](#)), to biocrusts on
203 dune slopes of the Gurbantünggüt Desert ([Li et al 2014](#)) and early-stage crusts from the Colorado Plateau
204 ([da Rocha et al., 2015](#)). In our study, cyanobacteria composition was held constant and thus the differences
205 found in germination and growth across plant species is likely attributable to seed traits ([Zhang and Belnap](#)
206 [2015](#)). For example, one explanation for the positive effect of cyanobacteria on seeds of *Senna notabilis* is
207 that these seeds are known to germinate rapidly over a wide temperature regime when compared to other
208 native species of northern deserts in Western Australia ([Commander et al, 2017](#)). Given this species appears
209 to be programmed for rapid germination, a trait known to help some species in arid ecosystems ([Parsons](#)
210 [2012](#)), the added advantage of a bio-fertilizer may have been expressed in this early recruitment phase when
211 compared to other species evaluated.

212 Some studies have shown that the exopolysaccharides (EPS) surrounding cyanobacterial cells have a major
213 role in protecting these cells from stress in extreme environmental conditions such as desiccation ([Pointing
214 and Belnap 2012](#); [Chittapun et al. 2017](#)). These substances are capable of forming a microenvironment that
215 prevent water loss by buffering osmotic potential ([Rossi et al. 2007](#)). Therefore, recent research has focused
216 on the specific effect of EPS excreted by cyanobacteria on seed germination of arid plant species, obtaining
217 higher rates of germination with addition of these substances ([Xu et al. 2013](#)). The positive effects of the
218 locally-sourced cyanobacteria species used in this study (*Nostoc microscopicum* and *Microcoleus
219 paludosus*) on particular species is likely related to their capacity to produce EPSs, which makes them
220 potentially ideal candidates for bio-fertilization of native plant species.

221 Although seeds of *Acacia hilliana* germinated in similar proportions under all treatments, there was a
222 notable effect on seeds soaked in the control BG11 solution (Control- BG11) (Figure 2), and they did not
223 develop further to produce healthy radicle and shoot growth (Fig. 3b, Fig. 4). The negative effect of the
224 culture medium appeared to be counteracted by adding cyanobacteria, as seedling survival and growth of
225 *Acacia hilliana* was not affected in seeds bio-primed with cyanobacteria + BG11 (Fig. 3b, Fig. 4). BG11
226 (Broth w/ Minerals) is a universal medium for the cultivation and maintenance of blue green algae
227 (cyanobacteria) that has been extensively used in inoculation experiments ([Rossi et al., 2017](#)), and is mainly
228 composed of salts in the form of sodium nitrate (NaNO₃) ([George et al., 2014](#)).

229 Some studies have reported that the presence of soluble salts can suppress plant growth. This could be seen
230 by small reductions in growth for several of our study species in the BG11 medium. However, in susceptible
231 species, such as seen in the *Acacia*, interacting factors including the osmotic potential effect, ion toxicity
232 and antagonism can have much larger negative effects on growth ([Rehman et al. 2000](#); [Abari et al. 2011](#)).
233 Inhibition of seedling growth by sodium elements has been attributed to insufficient water absorption for
234 radicle emergence, or toxic effects on the embryo ([Azza et al. 2007](#)). Hosseini et al., ([2002](#)) suggested that
235 differences in sensitivity between germination and subsequent seedling growth in the presence of high salt
236 concentrations may be caused by several factors. One of the potential causes is that germination is less

237 responsive to high tissue Na⁺ concentrations than seedling growth ([Debez et al. 2004](#); [Kim et al. 2012](#)).
238 The role of cyanobacteria appears then to be critical for removing Na⁺ at this early seedling stage in *Acacia*
239 *hilliana*. Several studies have underpinned the ability of cyanobacteria not only to tolerate stresses that are
240 predominant in salt-affected soils, such as nutrient deficiency, salinity, drought and temperature increases,
241 but also to uptake Na⁺ for their growth and nitrogen fixation function. Thus, these organisms adopt various
242 mechanisms for salt tolerance and have been suggested to reclaim salt-affected soils ([Rossi et al. 2017](#);
243 [Singh et al. 2016](#)). Our results highlight the need for further assessment of the ability of cyanobacteria to
244 alleviate the negative effects of saline conditions in native species.

245 *4.2 Implications for direct-seeding practices in land restoration*

246 In addition to the beneficial effects of cyanobacteria on soil C sequestration, N fixation and soil stability,
247 to restore dryland ecosystems ([Budel et al. 2017](#); [Rossi et al. 2017](#)), this study underpins the potential role
248 for native seeds to be inoculated with beneficial cyanobacteria during early-stage seed applications and not
249 be detrimental to the critical plant regeneration stages of germination and seedling growth phases known to
250 be problematic for restoration success. The results of *Acacia hilliana* point towards a role for salt-tolerant
251 cyanobacteria in alleviating salinity stress during seedling growth, which can be important for seedling
252 recruitment and subsequent plant development in restoration. Salinity imposes serious environmental
253 problems in arid and semi-arid regions by limiting plant growth and productivity during all developmental
254 stages ([Anaya-Romero et al. 2015](#); [Azza et al. 2007](#)).

255 A critical consideration in the application of indigenous cyanobacteria for landscape-scale restoration
256 projects is the ability to grow substantial biomass ([Velasco Ayuso et al. 2016](#)). Moreover, how beneficial
257 cyanobacteria can be integrated into restoration settings remains to be tested but could be delivered in
258 combination with rapidly developing seed enhancement technologies such as seed coating, pelleting, and
259 priming approaches ([O'Callaghan 2016](#); [Erickson et al. 2017](#)). Developing novel formulations that maintain
260 the viability of both seeds and cyanobacteria inoculant during storage and application will be crucial for
261 using these technologies in large-scale restoration. This line of work provides an exciting opportunity for

262 scientists and on-ground practitioners to merge multiple research disciplines together to aid future land
263 restoration opportunities.

264 **5. Conclusions**

265 We found significant positive effects of bio-primed seeds with locally-sourced indigenous cyanobacteria
266 from the genera *Microcoleus* and *Nostoc* on seed germination and seedling growth of *Senna notabilis* and
267 *Acacia hilliana* respectively. No significant effects were observed on *Grevillea wickhamii*, *Triodia epactia*
268 and *Triodia wiseana*. Our results showed that the influence of cyanobacteria on early seedling development
269 is species-specific but overall, cyanobacteria did not have an inhibitory effect on any of the species studied.
270 This study highlights the potential role for native seeds to be inoculated with beneficial cyanobacteria
271 during early-stage seed applications and not be detrimental to critical germination and early seedling
272 growth, phases known to be problematic for restoration success. Further considerations such as the ability
273 to grow substantial biomass, and the most effective way to deliver seed and cyanobacteria inoculum will
274 be critical to upscale these applications to landscape restoration.

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283 **Data Availability**

284 Sequences used in this study are available for download from the NCBI short read archive (SRA) under
285 Bioproject number PRJNA310158. Cyanobacteria isolate sequences are available from GenBank under

286 accession numbers KU612238- KU612249. All other data generated or analysed during this study are
287 included in this published article (and its supplementary information files).

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424 **LIST OF TABLE CAPTIONS**

425 **Table 1.** List of five plant species native to the Pilbara region used in this study. Adapted from Bateman
426 et al (2016).

427 **Table 2.** Cyanobacteria isolates identified to genus and species level with viability for large-scale growth
428 where ‘-‘ indicates isolates did not outgrow 3 ml of media, ‘+’ indicates isolates did not outgrow 20 ml of
429 culture, ‘++’ indicates isolates were up-scaled to greater than 50 ml of media.

430 **LIST OF FIGURES CAPTIONS**

431 **Fig. 1** (a) Example of the top and bottom of cyanobacterial biocrusts sampled; Liquid cultures of (b) *Nostoc*
432 *microscopicum* and (c) *Microcoleus paludosus* and; Microscopy of (d) *Nostoc microscopicum* and (e)
433 *Microcoleus paludosus*.

434 **Fig. 2** Relative abundance of cyanobacterial orders (inner ring) and genera (outer ring) as determined via
435 genomic profiling.

436 **Fig. 3** (a) Seeds germinated and (b) survived seeds bio-primed with cyanobacteria (vs control) in water and
437 BG11 medium (Mean proportion \pm SE; n=100). Levels of significance: (*) $P < 0.05$; (**) $P < 0.005$; (***)
438 $P < 0.001$

439 **Fig. 4.** (a) Seedling shoot length and (b) seedling root length of seeds bio-primed with cyanobacteria (vs
440 control) in water and BG11 medium (Mean proportion \pm SE; n=100). Levels of significance: (*) $P < 0.05$;
441 (**) $P < 0.005$; (***) $P < 0.001$

442

443 **TABLES**

444 **Table 1.** List of five plant species native to the Pilbara region used in this study. Adapted from Bateman et
 445 al. (2016).

Family	Plant species	Life form (photosynthetic pathway)*
Fabaceae	<i>Acacia hilliana</i>	Shrub (C3)
Fabaceae	<i>Senna notabilis</i>	Shrub (C3)
Proteaceae	<i>Grevillea wickhamii</i>	Shrub or small tree (C3)
Poaceae	<i>Triodia epactia</i>	Grass (C4)
Poaceae	<i>Triodia wiseana</i>	Grass (C4)

446

447 **Table 2.** Cyanobacteria isolates identified to genus and species level with viability for large-scale growth
 448 where ‘-’ indicates isolates did not outgrow 3 ml of media, ‘+’ indicates isolates did not outgrow 20 ml of
 449 culture, ‘++’ indicates isolates were up-scaled to greater than 50 ml of media.

Isolate	Classification	Large scale growth
N1.1c	<i>Limnothrix</i> sp.	-
N1.2a	<i>Microcoleus paludosus</i>	+
N1.2b	<i>Limnothrix</i> sp.	++
N2.1a	<i>Leptolyngbya foveolarum</i>	-
N2.3ci	<i>Leptolyngbya</i> sp.	++
N2.5bi	<i>Microcoleus paludosus</i>	++
N1.11a	<i>Leptolyngbya</i> sp.	++
O1.5ai	<i>Calothrix</i> sp.	-
O1.5aai	<i>Calothrix desertica</i>	+
O1.6dii	<i>Nostoc microscopicum</i>	++
O2.4a	<i>Leptolyngbya</i> sp.	-
O2.9a	<i>Calothrix</i> sp.	-
O1.10bi	<i>Scytonema</i> sp.	+

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453 **FIGURES**

454
 455 **Fig. 1** (a) Example of the top and bottom of cyanobacterial biocrusts sampled; Liquid cultures of (b) *Nostoc*
 456 *microscopicum* and (c) *Microcoleus paludosus* and; Microscopy of (d) *Nostoc microscopicum* and (e)
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 461 genomic profiling.

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468 proportion \pm SE; n=100). Levels of significance: (*) $P < 0.05$; (**) $P < 0.005$; (***) $P < 0.001$

469

Oscillatoriophycideae

- *Phormidium* sp.
- *Phormidium murrayii*
- *Stanieria cyanosphaera*
- *Synechococcus elongatus*
- *Oscillatoria acuminata*
- Other Genera (n=13)
- Unclassified
- *Phormidium pseudopriestleyi*
- *Oscillatoria rosea*

Nostocophycideae

- *Brasilonema terrestre*
- *Calothrix* sp.
- *Aphanizomenon ovalisporum*
- *Scytonema* sp.
- *Brasilonema bromeliae*
- *Nostoc* spp. (n=7)
- *Cylindrospermum stagnale*
- *Nostoc muscorum*
- *Tolypothrix distorta*
- *Anabaena* spp. (n=5)
- *Scytonema* spp. (n=3)
- *Calothrix brevissima*
- *Brasilonema* spp. (n=2)
- Unclassified
- Other Genera (n=4)

Synechococcophycideae

- *Leptolyngbya* sp.
- *Chamaesiphon minutus*
- *Arthronema* sp.
- *Acaryochloris* sp.
- *Leptolyngbya antarctica*
- *Chamaesiphon subglobosus*
- Other (n=5)

Plant and Soil: Supplementary Material

Effects of indigenous soil cyanobacteria on seed germination and seedling growth of arid species used in restoration

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Supplementary Methods description

Isolation and identification of Cyanobacterial isolates

In July 2009, cyanobacteria were isolated on both nitrogen replete and deplete (BG11₀) forms of BG11. For each sample, 2 g of crust was vortexed in media and spread across BG11 and BG11₀ agar plates containing 10 µg ml⁻¹ cycloheximide. Plates were incubated at 25°C under a continuous light regime of 80 µmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹. Colonies of varying morphology were sub-cultured using sterilised loop, serial dilution and picking with pulled capillary pipettes techniques (Rippka 1988). Uni-cyanobacterial isolates were subsequently transferred to liquid media. Cyanobacteria were fixed with 40% Karo™ corn syrup (Ach Food Companies) and viewed under 100 x magnification with oil immersion using a Zeiss Axioskop microscope (Germany). Morphological identification to genus level was achieved using *Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology* (Castenholz 2001).

Extraction of genomic DNA from cyanobacterial isolates was performed using a modified xanthogenate-SDS (XS) nucleic acid isolation (Tillett and Neilan 2000). Briefly, harvested cells were transferred into XS buffer containing silica beads and subjected to disruption of at intensity setting of six, for 45 s using a FastPrep FP120 (BIO 101 Savant Instruments) cell disruptor. This was followed by incubation at 60°C for 3 h with cell disruption repeated after 1 h and vortexing carried out every 30 min. Cell debris was pelleted by centrifugation at 12000 g for 10 min. The supernatant was collected and extracted twice with 400 µl of phenol:chloroform:isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1) (Sigma). DNA was recovered via ethanol precipitation. The 16S small subunit of the cyanobacterial isolates was targeted using cyanobacteria specific primers 27F (AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG) and 809R (GCTTCGGCACGGCTCGGGTCGATA) yielding amplicons of 780 bp using previously described PCR conditions (Jungblut et al 2005). The amplicons were bi-directionally sequenced using a 3730 DNA Analyzer (Applied Biosystems) by the Ramaciotti Centre for Genomics (UNSW, Australia). Isolate sequence data was compared to

the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) Genbank® database using the BLASTn program to determine the closest sequence identities (39).

Phylogenetic reconstruction

A Maximum Likelihood (ML) tree was constructed in order to examine the phylogenetic relationships of the cyanobacterial sequences generated in this study in order to assign taxonomy and to determine what fraction of diversity was recoverable via isolation. Cyanobacterial pyrosequencing reads were extracted from the community library (12488 in total) and clustered at a distance threshold of 0.05, resulting in 561 OTUs. Of these, 54 OTUs each contributing greater than 0.25% of sequences reads were included in the tree, resulting in the inclusion of at least 85% of all cyanobacterial reads. Reference sequences were obtained from the NCBI GenBank nucleotide database with preference given to sequences from established the culture collections Pasture Culture Collection (PCC) and the Culture Collection of Algae at Goettingen University (SAG), as well as sequences of isolates or OTUs previously derived from biological soil crust. An alignment was generated using Muscle (Edgar 2004) and manually checked for parsimony. FindModel (HIV Databases, NIH) selected the General Time Reversible (GTR) model (Tavare 1986) to be the nucleotide substitution model that best fit the data. This model was selected along with the parameters of gamma distribution with optimised alpha and estimated proportion of invariable sites in PhyML 3.0 (Guindon et al 2010) to construct the phylogenetic trees. Branch support estimations were calculated using the Approximate Likelihood Ratio Test (aLRT) (Anisimova and Gascuel 2006).

Growth of cultures for bio-priming

After taxonomic identification, the cyanobacteria cultures were maintained for long term storage on slopes of BG11 media in 50 ml plastic tubes with lids loosely screwed on in low light

conditions. In May 2017, subcultures of each species were taken and transferred to 3 ml liquid BG11 under constant $80 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ of light. After approximately 4 weeks of growth, these were transferred to conical flasks with 20 ml of BG11 and placed on a shaker at 40 rpm. It was noted that for the filamentous types, these conditions produced globular colonies encapsulated in EPS with very few hormogonia. Rather, the best growth was observed to be on the glass at the air-water interface. To optimize these conditions for the whole colony, cultures were transferred to deep-pan petri dishes with 50 ml of media where growth accelerated and produced sufficient biomass for harvesting.

Supplementary Figures

Fig. S1: Maximum Likelihood tree of partial cyanobacterial sequences generated via high throughput sequencing and cultivation of isolates clustered at 97% similarity. OTUs from this study are shown in bold. Isolates are shown in bold italics. Isolates used for bio-priming are highlighted in red. Uncultured reference sequences shown with country of origin in italics. Reference strains from BSCs are shown with an asterisk. Grouping A=Nostocophycideae, B = Synechococcophycideae, C=Oscillatoriothycideae. Circles at branch nodes represent aLRT support, large means greater than 80%, small means greater than 50%.

Fig. S2. Proportion of germinated seeds (T_{50}) with cyanobacteria (vs control) in water and BG11 medium.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Description of the genus assignment via microscopy and via phylogeny of the cyanobacteria isolates.

Isolate	Genus assignment via microscopy	BLASTn of partial 16S rDNA				Genus assignment via phylogeny
		Closest GenBank sequence	Sequence Identity (%)	Source	Accession	
N1.1c	<i>Limnothrix</i>	Uncultured Oscillatoriales clone	98	Desert - India	JF707584.1	<i>Oscillatoriales</i>
		Pseudanabaenaceae cyanobacterium HTT-U-KK3	93	Desert - USA	EF654069.1	
N1.2a	<i>Porphyrosiphon</i>	<i>Microcoleus paludosus</i> Es_Yyy1400	96	BSC - Southern Africa	KC463185.1	<i>Microcoleus paludosus</i>
N1.2b	<i>Limnothrix</i>	Oscillatoriales cyanobacterium Es_Yyyy700	95	BSC - Southern Africa	KC463178.1	<i>Oscillatoriales</i>
N2.1a	<i>Leptolyngbya</i>	<i>Leptolyngbya foveolarum</i> Komarek 1964/112	97	Subaerophyte - Czech Republic	X84808.1	<i>Leptolyngbya</i>
N2.3ci	<i>Leptolyngbya</i>	Uncultured clone	98	BSC - Oman	GU362222.1	<i>Pseudanabaena</i>
		<i>Pseudanabaena</i> sp. Es_Yyy1300	96	BSC - Southern Africa	KC463184.1	
N2.5bi	<i>Porphyrosiphon</i>	Uncultured clone	99	BSC - Oman	GU362215.1	<i>Microcoleus</i>
		<i>Microcoleus</i> sp. PCC 7113	96	Soil - USA	NR_102467.1	
N1.11a	<i>Leptolyngbya</i>	Uncultured clone	97	BSC - unknown	JQ770069.1	<i>Leptolyngbya</i>
		<i>Leptolyngbya</i> sp. CENA534	95	Saline Alkaline Lake - Brazil	KF246500.1	
O1.5ai	<i>Calothrix</i>	Uncultured clone	97	Human Skin	JF193441.1	<i>Nostoc</i>
		<i>Anabaena</i> sp. 0830-A	96	Lake - Japan	AB936775.1	
O1.5aai	<i>Calothrix</i>	<i>Calothrix desertica</i> PCC 7102	97	Desert - Chile	AF132779.1	<i>Calothrix</i>
O1.6dii	<i>Nostoc</i>	<i>Anabaena</i> sp. Ms2	97	Lake - China	HM573452.1	<i>Anabaena</i>
O2.4a	<i>Leptolyngbya</i>	Uncultured clone	97	Quartz hypolith - unknown	HM240924.1	<i>Oscillatoriales</i>
		<i>Arthronema africanum</i> SAG 12.89	93	Clay soil - Nepal	AB115966.1	
O2.9a	<i>Calothrix</i>	Uncultured clone	97	Carbonate surface - China	KF037788.1	<i>Calothrix</i>
		<i>Calothrix</i> sp. PCC 7715	96	Thermal Spring - France	KM019959.1	
O1.10bi	<i>Scytonema</i>	<i>Scytonema</i> sp. IAM M-262	94	Unknown	AB093483.1	<i>Scytonema</i>

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